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The Dynamics of Fixity and Freedom of Borders in Mamang Dai's *The Black Hill*

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Abstract:

This paper explores Mamang Dai's historical novel *The Black Hill* (2014) for the reconstruction of indigenous history. The paper focuses on the dilemmas of a changing relationship for the ethnic people to land and belonging under the impact of colonization. The paper argues while the author revives the Abor culture in the novel through storytelling, the narrative resists the dialectic of colonizer versus indigenous. Rather, it privileges blurred histories emerging from mobility around precolonial borders and the ensuing irreversible assimilation as an outcome of the colonial and missionary influence. In the process, the consciousness in the novel seems aligned with the critical border thinkers Gloria Anzaldúa and Walter D. Mignolo, as a decolonial project. While Dai's novel privileges the self-representative border consciousness with the imperative of making the culture relevant in the past and future, the creative narrative is not confined to the theoretical framework.

Keywords: border consciousness, blurred histories, land, mobility, belonging.

Introduction

Contemporary author, Mamang Dai blends creativity with ethnography of indigenous cultures from northeastern India in her writings in English. Her literary works, simultaneously unique

and representative, preserve and explore the collective identity of the Adi communities, primarily located in present day Arunachal Pradesh. Dai's historical novel, *The Black Hill* (2014), depicts the loss of ethnic ways of life, disrupted by British colonial administration in the 19th century. This paper examines the delineated novel's exposé of the angst wrought by European intervention and nostalgia for the traditional ways, specifically in relation to changing ties to land. However, the paper argues, the narrative moves beyond this portrayal revealing a distinctive consciousness ensconced in "blurred histories" tied to mobility around borders. Through Dai's exploration, competing land-centred philosophies, mobility and belonging allow for a nuanced identity-in-the-making. The novel also invites comparison between Dai's border consciousness with Gloria Anzaldúa's concept of "mestiza consciousness" closely aligned with recent critical border thinking frameworks (Walter Dignolo), often posited in opposition to colonial and hegemonic power structures. Dai's efforts to revive precolonial experiences and cultural systems align with the objectives of critical border thinking, which underscores indigenous methods of knowledge dissemination. Such approaches seek to recognize the epistemic contributions of marginalized groups as part of broader decolonial projects. Conversely, this paper asserts, the novel addresses both symbolic and physical borders to forge an alternative paradigm through storytelling that considers the complexity of intermingling pre- and postcolonial ethnologies, rejecting marginalisation. This extends the relevance of the novel beyond provincial labels and theoretical constructs. Rather, Dai's novel redefines and reinvigorates identity and borders as dynamic spaces for emerging of new identities, ensuring cultural relevance for the present and the future.

Recentring a Multilayered Consciousness

The Black Hill simultaneously evokes borderland consciousness and relative scepticism towards too much "border instinct" through a multilayered narrative. The author unfolds the

past from the present by intertwining the narrative persona of a woman in the Prologue with the story of the young woman protagonist Gimur. The narrative includes the historically ignored woman's negotiation with collective identity and belonging in relation to land. Such insight offers differing political and ethical attitudes to land that shape evolving perspectives on attachment and detachment to land, which underpin a non-binary consciousness. The narrative persona claims, it is the story of a people, "who wanted to exchange their old selves for a new life" (viii). The statement broadly suggests the cyclical patterns of life and death, and particularly the loss of old ways but with the aspiration for a renewed future. It also alludes to the creative act of writing to conserve an endangered culture. She further emphasizes, "how all the stories of the world are connected", yet there are more stories "that are silent and separate" (viii). The storytelling mode is a vivid attempt to highlight the unwritten narratives as well as recapture the authentic voice of oral cultures. The novel develops from the inevitable combination of creative and ethnographic re-examination of the past, a necessary role for writers depicting life in the northeastern region in the absence of indigenous written history or script. Dai's objective is to recover stories "misplaced yesterday or a thousand years ago" (viii) and counter the records on the "yellowed paper" a reference to the biased European literature that typically reduced the communities to primitive natives as justification of the colonial empires. However, Dai does not replace one culture with another in simplistic binaries of native/outsider, indigenous/colonial. Instead, she highlights the mixed-up realities of the ethnic and colonial eras to revitalize her culture in the past and have agency in the present and future.

The self-representative novel reconstructs ethnic identity by delving into oral intergenerational past dependent on memory and extant traditions of the Adi communities. It incorporates the interdependence and relatedness of the different clans and villages with each other, rather than an isolationist view of the traditional Adi (Abor in the novel) identity. The narrative privileges the insider's perspective against the hegemonic colonial documentation

without idealising the preterit. Simultaneously, the novel recentres precolonial borders and traditional claims to land. The ethnic Abor and Mishmee clans in the novel demonstrate awareness of the political and cultural ethos of adjoining areas perceiving themselves as gateways or borderlands to Tibet and China, and the plains of Assam and Bengal. The strategic locations of the Abor and Mishmee settlements is evident in the recurrent forays by the British East India Company armies. The novel commences in 1847, a significant year for the local communities encountering the British armies, and concludes in 1855, highlighting the undeniable reality of the establishment of British military and administrative control in large parts of the region. These combine with the European missionaries to create a hard and soft face of colonisation in the region.

In the novel, borders are both fixed and porous. The village life revolves around them, creating enclosures for continuity of traditions in the heterogenous oral cultures. The borders highlight the dominant role of topography, as most borders were aligned along major physical features. Hence, these borders seem inherent and organic to the ethnic communities living around them, implying that nature, borders and identity were inseparable. Historically, the insularity of the northeastern states of India is related to the formidable barriers formed by the hills and mountains of the Eastern Himalayas. The eponymous black hill in the novel is a steep mountain that separates the communities on either side as well as inspires reverence and awe. The author recounts enduring philosophical and moral lessons symbolized by the mountain, contrasted with the transience of those living around it and the fleeting nature of land possession. Critics highlight the recurring nature motifs in Dai's works, especially the symbolism of the mountain. Harpreet Vohra suggests, "the mountain is like an oracle, telling stories of change and yet bearing the nature of permanence" (48). The critic also asserts that the mountain represents a lasting connection with the environment beyond just childhood memories. Dai reiterates the existential truth that "Nothing is certain", yet acknowledges the

certainty associated with the mountain (*An Obscure Place*). The glistening black mica hill forms the backdrop of the narrative as a natural border and gains in meaning and metaphor as it witnesses the transformations in the lives of the three main characters Gimur, Kajinsha and Father Krick.

Gimur is from the Mebo village belonging to the Abor community distinguished by a blue cross tattoo on the chin of each member. At seventeen years of age Gimur has acquired the domestic and agricultural skills similar to other women of the village but stands out as an unconventional woman. She is described, “uncontrollable and daring”, often chided by her male friend Lendem or her mother for taking interest in spheres of life from which the women were excluded. For instance, she openly stares to seek signs of change in the demeanour of the “God-like” Mebo men resplendent in their traditional feathers and weapons, who had ventured to meet the “migluns” (strangers), rather than hide her face (11-12). Gimur’s motivation is her anxiety to know the outcome of the meeting with the white strangers wanted to set up a trading post near the village. The narrative captures the significant juncture of intervention by the British East India Company with its weapons and army in the village life. The men have just returned after meeting Captain Hamilton Vetch, the Political Agent of Upper Assam, stationed there to protect and strengthen British interests. Two years later, Gimur witnesses the new reality of the migluns setting fire to a nearby village. For Gimur, wars with other tribes were familiar lore, but “war with the British” was “a new thing” (24). Each clan defended its borders consisting of a few sparsely populated villages rigorously. The text suggests, precolonial borders were not entirely peaceful, although intermittent efforts towards peace were undertaken. Traditional inter-tribal conflicts were perceived as preservation of one’s territory, rather than expansion, and therefore, in sync with larger goals of peaceful co-existence (Miri). Dai’s depiction of the past renders the above perception of wars arguable, however, it underscores a strong sense of belonging inspired within the borders and generally to the land.

Gimur too expresses “fierce joy” in the possibility of war with the “migluns” representing traditional pride and independence of the tribe, “to teach them a lesson” (24). Simultaneously, the author raises pertinent questions regarding the rationale for wars and assumption of linear equations between territorial nativism, identity and belonging primarily through Gimur’s perspective on land.

Borders and Intersubjective Complexity

The narrative unfolds the complexity of the intersubjective realities of the ethnic past and in the period of transformation under colonialism. In 1850, Gimur witnesses a large gathering of leaders from various clans aiming to resist the British. Simultaneously, her personal and political life get enmeshed irrevocably. Amidst this, she spies a stranger, later revealed as Kajinsha, a great warrior from the Mishmee people, secretly visiting Mebo village to track British camps after his own village is destroyed by the colonial forces. As the young couple fall in love, Gimur experiences personal dilemma in her relationship with Kajinsha, a stranger from another tribe. Marrying him would hurt Abor pride, as inter-tribal relationships were betrayals and taboo. Faced with limited choices, she opts to leave her village quietly to live with Kajinsha in his distant home, despite feeling scared of the unfamiliarity ahead.

The journey to Kajinsha’s land takes several days of great physical strain over difficult terrain, especially as Gimur is pregnant. Apart from Kajinsha’s skills at camouflaging in the forests and navigating formidable terrain, Gimur becomes aware of political secrecy as well as strategic socialising that earned him great respect among various chiefs and clans on the way to his home, as did his reputation as a great warrior. The novel focuses on the peculiar location of Kajinsha’s home in the Mishmee hills, lying between Tibet and Ahom (present day Assam). For the local inhabitants, cross-border interactions for trade, social relations, and negotiations, were just as prevalent, as conflict. As a gateway to Tibet his village is of interest for European

missionary activities and colonial ambitions. Kajinsha's tribe defended against the British, while maintaining peace pacts with the Tibetans to restrict access to their villages. The descriptions of these journeys for peace or war draw attention to the porousness of the borders. The author emphasizes border consciousness as a distinctive feature of the villages, specifically, the dual consciousness of the Mishmee region as border and frontier.

Accordingly, Kajinsha grew up amid war and death. His father, a great Mishmee Chieftain, travelled far in his attempts to unite traditionally warring tribes in a bid to thwart the deeper inroads of the British with their firearms, salt, iron, tobacco and opium. He fails in securing stable alliances between the Tibetans and Mishmee chiefs. Dai attributes the reasons to, "Steeped in isolation, the tribes living in one valley across from the other viewed their neighbours with suspicion and dread. Claims over land, possession of rivers and streams and ownership rights to hunt and fish, regularly erupted into bloody, inter-tribal feuds and no one knew when the fighting would end" (15). However, his father perceived land as a place of "ownership and rest", without peace it would remain a dream. Increased encroachments by Tibetan nomadic groups such as the wily Chief Marpa's Tibetan Brokpa camps into Mishmee land, across previously unclaimed high valleys where the animals roamed free, forced him to recognise it as territory to be defended. Tired of the wars, Kajinsha's father brokered peace deals with the Brokpa herdsmen. One such measure was to arrange Kajinsha's marriage at an early age with Chief Marpa's niece Auli, an ailing woman. Despite the marriage, the "border was never settled" (100). Eventually, Kajinsha's father was killed fighting against the British.

As the new Chief, Kajinsha attempts to strengthen his father's efforts at peace. For him, the border is a subjective space of "social experimentation". He marries a Mebo girl from a different tribe against convention, like his first marriage. He understands Gimur's father helped the British in the same battle in which his father was killed. Later he defends Gimur as a representative of Abors who become tainted as helpers of the British. Thus, the reader is

reminded of the inter-subjective realities of the people that resists dialectical interpretation of their lives. He is a lone figure of tenuous peace who recognises the simultaneous value of borders and their porousness, a defender against annihilation of the borders and their relationality. As the couple traverse the challenging hills and forests, Kajinsha reveals to Gimur the many plots and betrayals defining his people's relationship with those they meet on the way. He points out Chief Lamet's house who had opened the way to white men. "These were old enmities kept alive by succeeding generations, and the root of conflict, it seemed to Gimur, was always about land" (65).

The journey with Kajinsha triggers a series of questions in Gimur's mind regarding the centrality of land in their lives. She wonders, "What is this land? Men spoke of land as a possession. From this stream to the limits of the jungle and up to that hill with the white rock is my land,' they said. Every piece of earth was claimed" (65). Dai does not idealize the underlying ethos of bloodshed over land. Further, she problematises the binaries of territorial versus non-territorial claims to land through Gimur's detached attitude. She had experienced freedom as she folded her few possessions in a bundle preparing to elope, at home in the lap of nature moving from place to place despite the discomforts. She has no qualms in leaving "nothing" and "no trace of herself" (50). Significantly, she felt no attachment to the village home, fields and the land. It was the traditional joy and celebrations of sending away a bride that Gimur missed. She proves possessiveness to be an unnecessary burden when she leaves her village to live with Kajinsha. For years, the preoccupation with land remains a troubling question for her. The reply by her mother that it was precious because it was her birthplace, did not satisfy Gimur. The shamans of her village emphasized the mutual belonging of the people born there with the land, "It is the soul of our ancestors. Where would we be, what would we do, without this land?" (66). Later she comprehends the meaning of her mother's explanation that land was "everything". However, she remains sceptical of the materialism entailed in the

concept of land. Dai uses this opportunity to raise a moral question, so what if one is born in a place (66) to destabilise the presumption of being born in a place as an ethical basis for claiming land such as embedded in violence over borders. Through Gimur, Dai divests belonging with a masculine and imperial idea of territoriality. Rather, the author stretches the dimensions of border consciousness that can simultaneously mingle and sustain intersectionality of detachment and belonging, territorial and non-territorial identity to accommodate contradictory claims for a peaceful life.

Border Consciousness and the Question of Decoloniality

The author's new consciousness appears parallel to disruption of "unitary aspect of each new paradigm" (Anzaldúa 80). In the novel, each clan or tribe views itself as independent or at the centre. It prevents them from forming new pacts to protect their borders without wars (Rexlin and Latha). Contemporary Borderland theorist Gloria Anzaldúa invites attention to a feminist view of culture and margins in colonial contexts. Anzaldúa enhances the reader's attention towards the state of "in betweenness" as a preferred and empowered space in theorizing of "borderland consciousness" that can potentially preserve contradictions. For her, the borderland is a place for transforming the pain and isolation of "in-betweenness" into an experience of agency through the construction of "mestiza consciousness" (*La Frontera*). Her experience as a Chicana woman growing up in a place of "invisible border", described as neither Mexico nor United States of America (located between Mexico and Texas), but somewhere as an immigrant at the margins of both, allow her to read metaphorical significance into borders as marginalisation. In her work, borderlands are sites of resistance to divisions. They embody contradictory movements and situate mestiza consciousness as an activity or process of the non-unitary subject, as hybrid spaces. At a personal level, she finds herself unable to fit the normative boundaries of gender, sexuality, or any identity. Accordingly, she

stresses on borderlands as also where identity is formed, however the grounding of this identity is not unitary, fixed or stable, rather it remains evolving, borne out of living within multiple worlds at once. Thus, she fights dualisms such as gendered expectations, colonial binaries and cultural hegemonies that form a barrier to decolonization of the inner self (Hammad). Her work also underlines mobility as an important constituent of border consciousness merging topographic lines with symbolic lines.

The cultural feminist's stress on mobility and non-binary worldview is comparable to Dai's expansive border consciousness in the novel. Dai undercuts the isolationist view of the community through emphasis on the porousness of the borders entailing mobility. She writes that borders were drawn in sand. Kajinsha's worldview is a result of mobility, for which he remains the "nomadic other" to the tribes. "The story of the novel is neither about the people of Tibet nor about the people of Northeastern India, but about the settlers and by-passers of the hill" (Rexlin and Latha 602). The author highlights Kajinsha's adaptability and ability to understand the different languages and knowledge systems because of multiple journeys. "We are afraid," Kajinsha tells Gimur, "because we do not travel" (37).

However, Dai, unlike Anzaldúa, does not extend her notion of the borderland to include any marginalized group or experience seemingly to belong nowhere, rejected or negated. While the borders evoke esoteric connections, myths, folklore, rituals and traditions, borderland for Dai is not necessarily another metaphor for all kinds of otherness as suggested through Anzaldúa's work. Further, the mestiza is rooted in a crisis that materializes as a constant rejection of identity, contrary to the ethnographic impulse of the novel. Gimur's expressions of freedom are similar to Anzaldúa's, however, the protagonist remains bound by the clan system. Dai admits she did not conceive of her women characters, such as Gimur, as rebels in the modern sense, rather, "They are women of the tribe who protect family and clan. They are women who can also break tradition and are ready to pay the price. Women have

always been doing this at different times throughout history” (Sarangi). Through the novel, the writer attempts to give due space and recognition to women conventionally excluded from chronicles of history. Dai comments, “Women were anonymous, forgotten in the story of blood lines. But every once in a while there was a sudden bend in the road, a separate heartbeat that made someone into a wild woman; a wild gene embedded in the marrow, like destiny waiting to be nudged into an all or nothing passion” (60). The novel intertwines Gimur’s story with the broader historical and cultural impacts of colonialism, emphasizing the resilience and agency of its characters, particularly women, in the face of change and adversity. Dai does not lose sight of rendering collective identity relevant and inseparable from the multiple ways of inhabiting borderland.

he layered narrative points to new dilemmas with the appearance of Father Nicholas Krick in Kajinsha and Gimur’s life, deeply shaking the already feeble bonds between the tribes. The French Jesuit priest arrives from Lorraine in France, in the wake of rising British dominance over South Asia and the Far East. His objective is to find a way to Tibet through the rebellious communities, challenging weather and terrain. His inspiration is steeped in the “spell” cast by Tibet’s mystique and remoteness in the days of the Christian martyrs in pursuit of extending the domains of Christianity. Dai describes in some detail the historical rise and decline of Christianity from the Middle Ages to the 19th century in Tibet and China as she explores the reasons for the arduous and committed voyages undertaken by the apostles. Her insight into the Jesuit zeal of missionary work for the Roman Catholic Church sets the context for Father Krick’s devotion to serve the people and proselytize simultaneously.

Kajinsha secretly follows Father Krick’s sojourns as he passes through his territory seeking the way to Tibet. He distrusts Father Krick, who faces challenges preaching in Tibet and settles temporarily in the Mishmee village. Despite the wariness an empathy develops between the three characters. Father Krick’s arrival coincides with Gimur’s personal tragedy

including the loss of one of her twins and marital disillusionment. To Gimur, the black hill becomes symbolic of a climb but never reaching the summit. Her anxieties increase as she dreams that someone has died in her village. In such a state, she finds solace in the sudden music emerging from Krick's flute. Later she meets him again in Mebo village, to which she has returned feeling alienated from Kajinsha, enduring the death of the second child on the way, and hearing the news of her mother's death upon arrival. Krick senses Gimur's pain though she remains silent and feels some connection with the Mebo as he is filled with wonder at the tattoo of the cross. Dai has been criticized for her sympathetic portrayal of Father Krick. But her acceptance is situated in the irreversible blurred lines she inherits. Thus, the author's perspective emerges from the present looking at the inevitability of an altered past. However, the author does not leave the devastating impact of the Europeans unproblematized. For instance, she explains in the novel, both Abor and Mishmee are exonyms, and not the identity selected or preferred by the respective communities. In one of the conversations, Kajinsha confronts the French priest, demanding, "why you have come here to tell us of a God you say is more powerful than any other god" (122). Kajinsha, confident of his deep and profound connection to the land, its material and esoteric value, is critical of the priest. He asserts that while Krick and the lamas derive their knowledge from books, the indigenous people learn from the land itself, seeing it as their book and interpreting natural elements as spiritual messages (122-23). This philosophy values living in harmony with nature and taking only what can be returned, fostering a sense of belonging to the land. Significantly, land also provides for them insights into the morality of right and wrong. In these conversations between the priest and Kajinsha, the concept of Donyi-Polo reflects the Abor community's belief in the sacredness of all life and the interconnectedness of man and nature. Indigenous views on sovereignty emphasize protecting land and relationships, contrasting with Western notions of territorial control for profit and power.

Conversely, Anzaldúa and Walter D. Mignolo, premise their theories on the basis of deconstructing borders as not natural or divine, but rather created in the very constitution of the modern/colonial world. Accordingly, in order to destabilise the Eurocentric construction of borders, it is important to foreground local histories and colonial subjectivities (Mignolo and Tlostanova 210). At the same time, for the novelist, borders are geographic as well as spiritual entities as has been evident in the relationship between the ethnic people and nature. The quest for decoloniality as framed by critical border thinking is based on rediscovering and privileging indigenous cultural and epistemic forms to sever ties with colonial and cultural hegemony. However, the delinking from colonial or European modes of thinking and dissemination of knowledge refers to the underlying colonial versus native framework in the attempt to replace ethnic with the western. The creative writer demonstrates a different relationship to the centre/ margin, both in the conception of borders and the language through which it is reconstructed in the historical novel unlike the typical West/East framework visualized by Mignolo.

As a result of his multiple journeys in the region, Krick's outlook towards other forms of belief he encounters among the various tribes appear liberal and his adventures those of an explorer. However, Father Krick with his "sextant and the cross", introducing modern medicine, new religion, language, and script, symbolizes the overpowering cultural shifts. His presence ultimately leads to significant disturbances, representing the soft face of colonialism. Dai coincides the political with the personal in the novel. Kajinsha, caught in a complex web of suspicion surrounding Father Krick's murder becomes a victim of treachery orchestrated by Chief Marpa and Lamet, implicating him in the incident. Krick dies in Gimur's arms, as she appears a mother-like figure to him, while she is greatly affected by his death. Six years later, a British battalion locates Kajinsha and imprisons for the presumed killing of Krick and his assistant Bourri. Though Gimur undertakes a dangerous journey alone to visit Kajinsha with

great difficulty, killing two prison guards in a bid to free him, she fails. Kajinsha is executed, but the author undercuts idealizing Kajinsha's death by highlighting the internal and external manipulations within the social context.

The broader interplay of empathy, conflict and adaptations inform the realities from which new identities emerge. In his last visit to the Mebo village, Father Krick is accepted by villagers as a healer and medicine man, reflecting his growing influence. Lendem, as the leader of Mebo, once opposed to aiding Father Krick, eventually acknowledges the need for change, stating, "We can sing new songs... 'Our miri, padari and his cross, the miglun gods, there is no contest here" (165). Thus, Dai's narrative underscores border consciousness as a space for cultural refashioning, a willingness to embrace transformation for peace and a deeper understanding of their beliefs. By blending mixed histories and moving beyond nostalgia she portrays the potential for evolving identities and reconciliation within communities.

The novel also draws attention to Gimur's love for the alphabet that she practises often. It is a gift passed down from her grandmother Moi who had received books and a pencil from the wife of a British priest during her husband's service defending the British garrison against his own people. Moi and Gimur are early precursors of the eventual dominance of English as the new language and script in the region. In this context, it is important to draw attention to critical Border theory raising the significant factor of language in the process of "delinking" with the Westphalian and colonial ways of thinking and controlling knowledge. Language plays a vital role in the recovery of local culture, history and forms of knowledge. Though, the writer has no choice but to use the words that political /linguistic hegemony impose, however, there is possibility of using that word beyond the mono-logic interpretation from the hegemonic perspective (Mignolo).

By the end of the novel, Gimur is left isolated and grappling with the profound connection she feels to the land. Staring at the black hill in the distance she reflects, "All this

time my heart and its longing have been tied up with these features—these hills, this sunset, this cold dawn and icy wind. The land has bred this. We are one” (66). Though initially engulfed in sorrow, she finds solace in this bond by deciding to return to her fields. This pivotal moment grants her a sense of purpose and belonging.

Conclusion:

Dai underscores the fragility of borders through the historical experiences of these communities. On the one hand she writes, “nothing stayed exactly the same”, and “empires and borders meant little. Their worlds could not be divided up, for they had lived in these lands for centuries, while empires had come and gone” (86). On the other, the shifting dynamics of territoriality throw the sentiment into crisis. Later through Father Krick’s realization, “he had been moving in a shifting world of water and sand and mountains” (175), the author reiterates the blurred histories and the ensuing border consciousness. Her work considers the realistic impact of hybridity and assimilation, not confined to nostalgia or hierarchical view of history. As depicted in the novel, shared beliefs have the potential to preserve the borders and the relationships between tribes. The borderland consciousness emerging from the novel prioritizes blurred histories and symbolic meanings, therefore, closely aligning with decolonial project. Simultaneously, Dai’s use of myths, folktales, rituals, philosophies and traditions interwoven with both the mother tongue and English showcases her skill in crafting historical fiction that opens up pathways for equal exchange between cultures with a view to the present and future. Dai’s ability to integrate the “other” without settling into rigid binaries, liberates nature, people, borders and identities into a fluid interconnected framework that resists specific categorization of genre and theory.

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